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A REVIEW: HERB-DRUG INTERACTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Alternative medicine is becoming popular worldwide and this is clearly evident from the rapidly escalating sales figures. The time tested and clinically proven herbal medicines like *Aloe vera*, *St John's wort*, *Gingo biloba*, *Garlic*, *Ephedra* etc., make up most of the world's market as for as alternative medicine is concerned. Advances in western medicine have dramatically increased health conditions and life expectancy of people. In spite of the latest developments in allopathic system of medicine people still seek alternative and complimentary system. The use of herbal medicine to treat a wide range of conditions is rising rapidly, leading to increased intake of phytochemicals. Recent studies reveal potential fatal interactions between herbal medicines and drugs. Herbal medicine is amongst the 16 alternative systems of medicine, which is used to treat existing illness and also for preventive and health conditions. Herbs like *Aloe vera*, *St John's wort*, *Ginkgo biloba*, *Feverfew*, *Ginger* and *Kava* make most of the market. The increasing popularity of alternative therapies, including herbal remedies is a new challenge for health care providers because the evidence on safety for herbal remedies incomplete, complex and confusing. The herbal medicines are certainly associated with risks and benefits. Interaction between herbal medicines and drugs are based on the same pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic principles as like drug-drug interactions. Now present condition patients taking both ayurvedic and allopathic treatment remain aware of potential herb-drug interaction and avoid taking medications .which might prove hazardous to their already deteriorating health. This article provides brief idea about pharmacist can change the present scenario and utilize their knowledge in providing healthy information about herb-drug interaction.

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Introduction

Herb drug interactions are a hot topic of debate. Use of herbs and their preparations are coming under increasing attack for being potentially dangerous to patients who are already taking allopathic medications. The concerns are multiplied for those patients currently taking multiple medications often prescribed by different physicians.

The basic concept of interaction is that consumption of two substances (herbs, drugs, foods, liquids) at the same time, or within a short time of each other, will result in alteration physiological effects that are different from a simple summation of the effects of either taken separately, which is the basic definition of a non linear effects. Since the early 19th century attempts have been made to understand the actions and properties of traditional Chinese medicinal substances through scientific research.

Due to the fact that herbs are composed of a multitude of ingredients whose interactions with the body are exceedingly complex a high level of sophistication of research methodology is necessary to describe these interactions. Only recently has such a rigorous methodology begun to be developed. Most of the people today use herbal therapies along with prescription and non-prescription medications. Although considered natural, many of these herbal therapies can interact with other medications, causing either potentially dangerous side effects and or reduced benefits from the medications. Currently, there is very little information published on herb-drug interactions with the use of herbs is progressively growing across the world. When herbal therapies and drugs (prescription or non-prescription medications) are used together, they can interact in the body, causing changes in the way the herbs and/or the drugs work. Such changes are called herb-drug interactions. They can be beneficial or

harmful to you, depending on the type of interaction.

Herb-drug interactions can impact on health and the effectiveness of treatments. For example, some herbal therapies might

- ❖ Increase the side effects of drugs, possibly leading to toxicity
- ❖ Decrease the therapeutic effect of drugs, possibly leading to treatment failure.
- ❖ Modify the action of drugs, possibly leading to unexpected complications.
- ❖ Enhance the therapeutic effect of drugs, possibly leading to over medication.[1,2 & 3]

Herbs and their interaction with conventional drugs

Now a day, like drug-drug interaction and food-drug interactions, herb-drug interactions are becoming incredibly common. It is known that millions of patients are taking herbal and conventional medicines concurrently, often without the knowledge of their physicians and elevating the potential of herb-drug interactions. The matter of herb-drug interactions appears large over the practice of herbal medicine. Herbal drugs are the plants based products that are used to treat as herbs, herbal supplements, biomedicines or botanicals. When herbal drugs and conventional drugs are used together, they can interact in body, causing changes in the way the herbs and/or the drugs work. Such changes are referred as herb-drug interactions.

There are few herb drug interactions reported up till now but they cannot be unobserved as patients who are not aware about the adverse effects that can possibly occur due to concurrent administration of herbal and OTC drugs would have to face devastating consequences. The possible herb-drug interactions and resultant have been reported in table.1.[4 & 5]

Table 1: Possible herb-drug interactions.

S. No	HERBAL DRUG	INTERACTING DRUG[S]	COMPLICATIONS
1	Aconite (<i>Aconitum napellus</i>)	Anti hypertensive's	Toxicity increased or death ⁽⁶⁾
2	Agrnomy (<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>)	Anti coagulants	Decrease in clotting time ⁽⁷⁾
3	Aloe (<i>Aloe vera</i>)	Cardiac glycosides	Potentiate effect on heart ⁽⁸⁾
4	Angelica (<i>Angelica dahurica</i>)	Anti coagulants	Decrease in clotting time ⁽⁹⁾
5	Cascara (<i>Rhamnuspurshiana</i>)	Anti arrhythmic	Hypokalemia & sedation ⁽¹⁰⁾
6	Chilli peper (<i>Capsicum spp</i>)	Ace inhibitors	Formation of cough ⁽¹¹⁾
7	Garlic (<i>Allium sativum</i>)	Saquinavir	Plasma drug concentration decreased ⁽¹²⁾
8	Karela (<i>Momordica charentia</i>)	Chiorpropamide	Glycosuria ⁽¹³⁾
9	Papaya (<i>Carica Papaya</i>)	Warfarin	Skin, G.i.t, urinary bleeding and prolonged Prothrombin time ⁽¹⁴⁾
10	St John's wort	Indinavir	A 57% reduction in Indinavir AUC ⁽¹⁵⁾
11	Tamarind (<i>Tamarindus indica</i>)	Aspirin	Increased bioavailability of Aspirin ⁽¹⁶⁾
12	Yohimbe (<i>Pausinystalia yohimbe</i>)	Tricyclic antidepressants	Hypertension ⁽¹⁷⁾

Evidence and nature of herb-drug interactions

The evidence of interactions among such commonly used dietary supplements is often based on presumed pharmacologic activity, data derived from in-vitro or animal studies, or anecdotal single case reports and case series. Therefore, there is limited information to guide clinical decision making and to inform patients of safety issues related to herb-drug interactions. The nature of herb-drug interactions is not a chemical interaction between a drug and an herb component to produce something toxic. Instead, the interaction may involve having an herb component cause either an increase or decrease in the amount of drug in the blood stream. A decrease in the amount of drug could occur by herb components binding up the drug and preventing it from getting into the blood stream from the gastrointestinal tract, or stimulating the production and activity of enzymes that degrade the drug and prepare it for elimination from the body. An increase in the drug dosage could occur when an herb component aids absorption of the drug, or inhibits the enzyme that break down the drug and prepare it for elimination.

A decrease in drug dosage by virtue of an interaction could make the drug ineffective; an increase in drug dosage could make it reach levels that produce side effects. Alternatively, an herb

might produce an effect that is contrary to the effect desired for the drug, thereby reducing the drug effect, or, an herb might produce the same kind of effect as the drug and give an increase in the drug effect.

Determination of herb-drug interaction

The incidence of clinically considerable interaction between herbals and conventional drugs is unidentified. A feature that may account for the lack of data on the true prevalence of herbal-drug interactions is that information needed to determine whether an interaction has occurred is often unavailable owing to the following;

- ❖ Multiple ingredients.
- ❖ A lack of information concerning the "contents" of the herbal product.
- ❖ Incomplete or inaccurate product information.
- ❖ Poly Pharmacy.

Additionally, patients may not inform health care providers of suspected interactions, or they do not attribute the reaction to the natural product. Controlled clinical studies are needed to clarify and determine the clinical importance of herb-drug interactions. Considering, lack of understanding of herb-drug interactions, proper reporting of such cases, careful vigilance, evidence based appraisal and constantly updated reviews of such information are very important to promote understanding in this area [18 & 19].

Mechanisms of herb-drug interactions

1. Pharmacokinetic Interactions

Pharmacokinetic interactions involve changes in the way herbs and drugs move through body and can alter the amount, or level, of drug(s) in the body. If the interaction increases the level of a drug, you might experience side effects and/or toxicity. If the interaction decreases the level of a drug, it might not work as well, possibly leading to treatment failure and/or drug resistance. There are several places in the body where such interactions can happen.

Stomach: When herbs and drugs are taken orally, they are usually absorbed into the bloodstream through the stomach and intestines. Herbs can affect the way in which drugs are absorbed, leading to changes in the amount of drug that enters the bloodstream. For example, some herbs can change the physical environment of the stomach, such as the p^H level, while others might chemically bind to drugs, causing them to remain in the stomach instead of entering the bloodstream. Some herbs, such as laxatives, can speed up the digestive process, reducing the amount of time a drug is present to be absorbed by the stomach.

Liver: Once in the bloodstream, many drugs need to be metabolized (chemically altered) by the liver either in order to become therapeutically active or to be removed from the bloodstream. So the liver plays an important role in controlling the level and effectiveness of drugs in the body. Herbal therapies (and drug therapies, too) can change liver metabolism. By inducing or inhibiting liver enzymes, herbs can alter the amount of therapeutically active drug in the blood.

Kidney: some drugs are eliminated from the bloodstream through the kidney. Herbs that affect the functioning of the kidney can change the level of drug in the blood. If the herb reduces kidney function, the level of drug may increase. If the herb increases kidney functioning, the level of drug may decrease.

Pharmacodynamic Interactions

Pharmacodynamic interactions refer to the mutual actions of herbs and drugs inside the body. When

taken at the same time, herbs and drugs may work together (synergistically) or in opposition (antagonistically). For example, separately they can have the same toxic effects, so that when taken together, they cause increased side effects.

Many herb-drug interactions fall into this category. Pharmacodynamic interactions are difficult to predict or prevent than pharmacokinetic interactions. Most of the Pharmacodynamic interaction known now is documented through actual cases-as opposed to laboratory experiments. The best way to prevent Pharmacodynamic interaction is to follow the patient closely monitor all clinical responses including signs, symptoms and any abnormal reactions. Pharmacodynamic interactions affect a drug's action in a qualitative way, either through enhancing effects (synergistic or additive actions) or antagonizing effects. Many herb-drug interactions are Pharmacodynamic type and are difficult to predict or prevent [19, 20].

Risks of herbal – drug interactions

The risk of having an herbal- drug interaction is based on a variety of factors and not solely based on the pharmacologic and pharmacokinetic characteristics of the herbal. One important factor that increases the likelihood of having an herbal – drug interaction is concomitant use of an herbal with drugs that have a narrow therapeutic index. Such drugs include Digoxin, antiepileptic drugs, antineoplastic agents, immunosuppressant's and Warfarin. Patient populations who are at increased risk for having herbal-drug interactions include the elderly, critical care patients, patients undergoing surgical procedures, patients with liver or renal disease and patients receiving multiple medications[21].

Clinical management of herb-drug interactions

Clinical management of drug-drug interaction should include prospective and concurrent patient, disease and drug monitoring measures that are sensitive enough to alert the pharmacist or healthcare provider to monitor and whenever possible, correlate these findings with clinical laboratory tests. Follow up monitoring of a patient's therapy and making appropriate

adjustments in the drug regimen can circumvent potentially significant drug interactions.

Patients at high risk for drug interactions who also take drugs with narrow therapeutic index should be monitored more closely for drug interactions, especially when a new drug is added or discontinued. Depending on the drugs in question, likely drug interactions will generally occur within a few days following a change in drug regimen. If two drugs have been identified as

having high potential to interact and cause harm, the pharmacist can contact the patient's physician to obtain an order for another medication that will not cause the troublesome interaction. In some instances a patient's diet or lack of adherence to a specified diet may be part of the problem. These situations may require the assistance of a dietitian to resolve. In addition to the above guide, it is possible to predict when herb/drugs interact by knowing their pharmacokinetic properties and their Pharmacodynamic behaviours [22-24].

Table 2: Some of the reported herb-drug interactions.

HERB	DRUG	INTERACTION
<i>Momordica charantia</i> (MC)	Rosiglitazone	MC also augmented the hypoglycaemic activity of Rosiglitazone ⁽²⁵⁾
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Hypoglycaemic drugs	Synergistic antihyperglycemic effect ⁽²⁶⁾
<i>Guar gum</i>	Metformin, Glibenclamide	Decreases absorption of Metformin and Glibenclamide ⁽²⁷⁾
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Cholrpropamide	Less glycosuria ⁽²⁸⁾
<i>Garlic</i>	Cholrpropamide	Hypoglycaemic response ⁽²⁹⁾
<i>St john's wort</i>	Tolbutamide	Increases hypoglycaemia ⁽³⁰⁾
<i>Ginseng (Panax Ginseng)</i>	Insulin	Synergistic, anti diabetic actions of herb ⁽³⁰⁾
<i>St john's wort</i>	Rosiglitazone	Decreases drug effect ⁽³¹⁾

Evaluation of herbal–drug interactions

Fugh-Berman and Ernst have developed a rubric for the determination of the reliability of case reports on drug– herbal interactions [32]. The probability of an interaction is scored using a 10-point scale, where one point is given for each of 10 items such as such as patient medical history and event chronology. Table:1

Table: 1 Evaluation of the probability of herbal–drug interactions

- ❖ Evaluation of the probability of herbal–drug interactions.
- ❖ Adequate patient history (age, sex, relevant medical conditions) is reported.
- ❖ Concurrent diseases, conditions, or other medications associated with adverse event (including dosing).
- ❖ Concomitant medications are documented (including dosing).
- ❖ Description of integrators is adequate.
- ❖ Obvious alternate explanations have been excluded.

- ❖ Chronology is complete.
- ❖ Time sequence of drug administration to adverse event is reasonable.
- ❖ Adverse event is adequately described.
- ❖ Event ceases upon stopping drug.
- ❖ Event recurs upon rechallenge.

Warfarin-Herbal Drug Interactions

Warfarin is known to interact with many drugs and, owing to its narrow therapeutic index, interactions can result in potentially fatal consequences if either bleeding complications arise or if sub therapeutic levels occur. Herbals can also interact with warfarin, but the risk of herbal-warfarin interactions is difficult to characterize because of the limited number and nature of existing case reports. [33,34]

Herbals that may interact with warfarin are presented in Table 5. inhibit platelet-activating factor, or contain salicylates may increase the risk for bleeding. Interactions between warfarin and these herbals should be considered theoretical at

the moment. Still, until additional research becomes available, it would be judicious to discourage use of any of these herbs in patients taking warfarin or for those who are undergoing any type of surgical procedure. Some herbals contain coumarin derivatives, and bleeding could occur when these herbals are taken with warfarin despite coumarin being only a weak anticoagulant. Notably, coumarins can be converted to dicoumarol when preparations are stored improperly [35].

Vitamin K foods include green, leafy vegetables and certain vegetable oils; consuming appreciable amounts of these vitamin K-containing foods can antagonize warfarin. Some herbals also contain appreciable amounts of vitamin K, and consumption may also antagonize warfarin therapy. Case reports of vitamin K antagonism of warfarin by fiddleheads and noni juice have been documented. There is a case report of a 44-year-old man on chronic warfarin therapy with international normalized ratio (INR) [for anticoagulant monitoring] values of 2.5-3.5, who experienced a reduction in response to warfarin (INR 1.14 and 1.37) after consuming a large amount of green tea (one-half to 1 gallon daily) for about one week. 40 Within one week after discontinuing green tea, his INR returned to an appropriate value (INR 2.5).

The amount of vitamin K in dried green tea leaves is higher (1428 mcg of vitamin K/100 g of leaves) than in dried black tea leaves (262 mcg of vitamin K/100 g of dried black tea leaves). Brewing green tea lowers the amount of vitamin K (0.3 mcg of vitamin K/100 g brewed tea), although the actual concentration of vitamin K in the final product varies depending on the dilution and the amount of tea leaves used to brew tea. The reported interaction between green tea and warfarin may be attributable to the antiplatelet of green tea and not the vitamin K content. Drinking significant amounts of green tea should be avoided in patients receiving warfarin, although smaller amounts may not produce any appreciable clinical reduction in INR values [37].

Warfarin–garlic interactions

The current evidence that garlic may interact with warfarin is mainly based on case reports of patients who ingested excessive amounts of garlic and developed platelet disorders and/or Hemorrhage [38, 39, 40 and 41]. There is an unavailable report of 2 patients who developed elevated INR with concomitant use of garlic and warfarin 31. In vitro studies have found that garlic oil and the constituent ajoene inhibits platelet aggregation induced by various aggregating agents [42, 43 and 44]. But results of studies that evaluated the effect of garlic on platelet function in humans have been conflicting. A double-blind, placebocontrolled study in 14 men found garlic had no significant effect on platelet aggregation 45 and platelet aggregation was not altered with a 10-day course of garlic capsule in 4 healthy subjects. However, continued ingestion of large quantities of raw garlic cloves inhibited platelet aggregation [46]. And consumption of essential oil of garlic produced a dose-related inhibition of platelet aggregation in 6 health adults [47]. Patients using warfarin should be cautioned regarding the possible risk of increased bleeding with ingestion of garlic.

Warfarin–green tea interaction

There is a case report of a possible interaction in a 44 year-old patient who was on stable warfarin therapy for a mechanical heart valve. The patient experienced a decreased INR after consuming a large amount of green tea (1 gal/day for 1 week.) [48]. Oral administration of the probe drugs dextromethorphan (CYP2D6 activity) and alprazolam (CYP3A4 activity) to 11 healthy volunteers demonstrated that decaffeinated green tea (*Camellia sinensis*) extract did not induce CYP2D6 and 3A4 pathways. A study using rabbit whole blood found that green tea is a potent inhibitor of thrombin stimulated platelet thromboxane formation which suggests green tea extract may be beneficial for treatment of vascular disease, but may also increase the risk of bleeding when used in combination with antiplatelet and anticoagulant drugs [49]. Therefore, patients on warfarin therapy should not consume large quantities of green tea.

Role of pharmacist in preventing herb drug interaction

Pharmacist can play a vital role in preventing drug herb interaction to occur by appropriately dispensing medicine and taking due care of patient's history and medication profile. In order to ensure that the drugs that he is dispensing to the patient are safe and will not cause any interaction, he should ask following questions:

- ❖ Are you taking an herbal product, herbal supplement or other "natural remedy?"
- ❖ If so, are you taking any prescription or non-prescription medications for the same purpose as the herbal product?
- ❖ Have you used this herbal product before?
- ❖ Are you allergic to any plant products?
- ❖ Are you pregnant or breast-feeding?

Make sure your pharmacist and your doctor(s) know about every drug you are taking, including prescription and non-prescription drugs, herbal products, and any dietary supplements, including vitamins and minerals; Only take medication that has been specifically prescribed for you by your physician; Medication must be taken properly to ensure its safety and effectiveness; Unless otherwise instructed, take medicine on an empty stomach to achieve a faster onset of action; When taking medicine with food or around a meal time is not recommended, take medicine one hour before meal/food or two hours after meals or

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eating food; Take your medicine with a full glass of water.

Avoid concurrent use of alcohol with medicine. Avoid consuming excessive quantities of chocolate and beverages containing caffeine coffee, tea, colas and If you have any questions or concerns about your medicine or you believe you are having an adverse drug reaction or drug interaction, consult your pharmacist or physician immediately. If there is a problem, your pharmacist can contact your physician, who can prescribe other medication to avoid the risk of drug related problems. Hence patients prescribed with certain known herbs which are likely to produce interaction with conventional drugs should be periodically monitored. Interactions reported earlier can help to avoid their concurrent use.

Conclusion

Now present condition patients taking both ayurvedic and allopathic treatment remain aware of potential herb-drug interaction and avoid taking medications .which might prove hazardous to their already deteriorating health. This article provides brief idea about pharmacist can change the present scenario and utilize their knowledge in providing healthy information about herb-drug interaction.

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